

Hemp Club

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Competent and
Connected Cluster Unfold
the Hemp Industry Potential
for the European Bioeconomy

What we do

The HempClub project brings together **7 clusters and association** operating in the bio-economy, advanced manufacturing and hemp production sectors to create **interconnected and interregional supply chains** between operators in primary production, agri-food processing and green chemistry by strengthening industrial symbiosis and sustainable and renewable business models in the **hemp sector**.

- 🟡 Improve the **management skills** of cluster managers.
- 🟡 Enhance **collaboration** and **networking** activities between European organisations.
- 🟡 Strengthen **cluster excellence capacity** by improving the portfolio of business support services.
- 🟡 Promote **internationalisation, technology** and **knowledge transfer** through the activation of new opportunities for growth and capacity of excellence for clusters and their members.
- 🟡 **Facilitate B2B and C2C collaborative activities** to strengthen interregional strategies for the bioeconomy

Why hemp?

With its **unique chemical properties, environmental benefits, high yield and wide range of applications**, hemp is a valuable crop for the bioeconomy, contributing to achieving climate neutrality, although still representing a niche crop in Europe.

ClusterXChange

- ◆ ClusterXChange is a new pilot scheme to support short-term exchanges to better connect Europe's industrial ecosystems. It facilitates transnational cooperation, peer learning, networking and innovation uptake between actors of different industrial clusters.
- ◆ The project will carry out at least 80 short term exchanges involving SMEs, scale supports organizations, training providers, public authorities and big companies involved or interested in the hemp sector and belonging to a COSME participating country.
- ◆ Exchanges will include several activities such as on-the-job-training for visiting participants, sharing of information and experience between visiting organisation and host organisation, enhancing market access and identification of potential partners for new cluster organisations and other scaling-up support scaling-up support organisations, supporting the networking between clusters.
- ◆ Most of these exchanges will have a duration of five working days with a distance between the two involved organisations more than 200 kilometres. A lump sum will be provided to support accommodation and living costs during the exchange.

www.hempclubproject.com

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To take part in the
ClusterXChange,
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